

A SINGLE CASE STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF BALA DHATRYADI TAILA NASYA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ARDITA (FACIAL PARALYSIS)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ardita, a Vata Nanatmaja Vyadhi in Ayurveda, closely correlates with idiopathic facial paralysis or Bell's Palsy in modern medicine. It is characterized by the sudden onset of unilateral facial muscle weakness, leading to significant functional and psychosocial distress. Nasya Karma (nasal administration of medication) is a cornerstone treatment for Urdhva Jatrugata Vikara (disorders of the supraclavicular region). **Aim:** This single-case study aimed to evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of Bala Dhatryadi Taila Nasya in managing a case of Ardita. **Settings and Design:** A 42-year-old male diagnosed with Ardita was treated with a structured Ayurvedic regimen, with Nasya as the primary intervention. **Materials and Methods:** The patient underwent a 7-day course of Bala Dhatryadi Taila Matra Nasya (8 drops/nostril) following standard Purva Karma (preparatory procedures) and Paschat

Karma (post-procedural care). Concurrent internal medications included Dashamoola Kwatha and Ashwagandha Churna. **Assessment was based on clinical parameters:** lagophthalmos, deviation of the angle of the mouth, forehead wrinkling, cheek puffing, speech, and mastication. **Results:** Significant clinical improvement was observed over seven days. By Day 3, slight improvements were noted. By Day 5, facial asymmetry reduced markedly, and

by Day 7, the patient demonstrated near-normal eye closure, symmetrical smile, and clear speech. **Conclusion:** This study suggests that Bala Dhatryadi Taila Nasya, as part of a comprehensive Ayurvedic protocol, is a potent and effective intervention for Ardita. The results underscore the importance of Nasya therapy in pacifying aggravated Vata Dosha at the site of pathology, facilitating rapid neuromuscular recovery.

KEYWORDS: Ardita, Bell's Palsy, Nasya, Bala Dhatryadi Taila, Vata Vyadhi, Panchakarma, Ayurveda.

1. INTRODUCTION

Facial paralysis is a debilitating condition that results in the loss of voluntary muscle movement on one side of the face, primarily due to dysfunction of the seventh cranial (facial) nerve. In contemporary medicine, the most common form is Bell's Palsy, an idiopathic, acute peripheral facial neuropathy with an incidence of approximately 15-30 per 100,000 individuals annually.^[1] Standard management often involves corticosteroids, antiviral agents, and physiotherapy, yet outcomes can vary, and complications like synkinesis and incomplete recovery are not uncommon.^[2]

In the Ayurvedic paradigm, this condition is described in detail as Ardita (literally meaning "deviated" or "distorted"). Classical texts such as the Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita classify it under Vata Nanatmaja Vikara—diseases arising from the sole vitiation of Vata Dosha.^[3,4] The pathogenesis involves the aggravation of Vata, which then localizes in the Siras (channels) of the face, leading to the vitiation of the facial nerves (Vataja Snayu), causing symptoms like Mukhavakrata (deviation of mouth), Akshivinimilia (inability to open or close eyes), and Vakrastuta (slurred speech).^[5] The site of pathology, Shira (head), is considered the locus of all sensory and motor functions and the seat of Prana Vata.

वाताददितमापन्नो वक्रीभवति वै मुखम् ।

एकाक्षिणीं च निमिषेद् वक्रवागथ जृम्भते ॥ CHA.VI.1/21

वाताददितमापन्नो वक्रीभवति वै मुखम् ।

एकाक्षिणीं निमिषति स्तब्धेऽक्षिणी तथैव च ॥६॥

ललाटं जृम्भते वक्रं वक्रोच्चारस्तथैव च ।

अदितं नाम तं विद्याद्वातादेव न संशयः ॥७॥ SU.NI.1/6-7

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एकाक्षिणीं च निमिषेद्वक्रवागथ जृम्भते ॥ A.HRU.NI.16/47

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अदितं नाम तं विद्याद्वातात् सर्वाङ्गवेदना ॥ MA.NI.22/52

For diseases manifesting above the clavicle (Urdhva Jatrugata Roga), Nasya Karma (errhine therapy) is enumerated as the Shodhana (purification) treatment of choice. Acharya Charaka states, "Nasyamurdhno hi shodhanam" – Nasya is the cleansing therapy for disorders of the head.^[6] Nasya facilitates the direct administration of medication to the brain and cranial nerves via the highly vascular nasal mucosa and the olfactory pathway, a concept finding resonance in modern intranasal drug delivery systems.^[7]

नासा हि शिरसो द्वारं तस्मान्नस्यं प्रशस्यते ।

नस्यमूर्ध्वजटूरोगहरं वातविकारनुत् ॥७॥

शुद्धस्यापि हि नस्येन शिरः सुखमवाप्नुयात् ।

इन्द्रियाणि प्रसीदन्ति बलं वर्णश्च वर्धते ॥८॥ CHA.SI.1/7-8

शिरोग्रीवाग्रहारोगशिरोरुक्कर्णनादकाः ।

तिमिरं पिटिकास्वापो दन्तरुक् केशदूषिकाः ॥१८॥

हनुस्तम्भो भ्रुवोस्तम्भो गलशोषोऽक्षिरोगकाः ।

आध्मानं कासशोफौ च तथा गण्डूपदाकृमिः ॥१९॥

उरःशिरोऽभिघातौ च मन्यास्तम्भश्च जृम्भिका ।

एते नस्येन शाम्यन्ति रोगा उर्ध्वजटुर्गताः ॥ CHA.SI.1/18-19

Bala Dhatryadi Taila is a classical medicated oil formulation specifically indicated in Vata disorders affecting the nervous system.^[8] Its key ingredients, Bala (*Sida cordifolia*) and Dhatri (*Embllica officinalis*), are renowned for their Vata-shamaka (Vata-pacifying), Balya (strengthening), and Rasayana (rejuvenative) properties, making it an ideal candidate for neuro-muscular rehabilitation.

बलाद्वयममृता द्राक्षा शतावरी रसाञ्जनम् । एलां कुष्ठं विडङ्गं च पृथक् कर्षद्वयानि च ॥

तैलप्रस्थं जलद्रोणं पाचयेत् कुशलो भिषक् । पादशेषं ततः पूतं स्नेहं तत्र विपाचयेत् ॥

कण्डू कुष्ठं पामविस्फोटगण्डमालां तथाऽर्दितम् । अपस्मारं भ्रमं हन्यात्सर्वाङ्गव्यथमेव च ॥

SAHASTRAYOGA

This case study documents the application and outcome of a structured Ayurvedic treatment protocol centered on Bala Dhatryadi Taila Nasya in a case of Arditā, aiming to provide clinical evidence for this traditional therapeutic approach.

2. PATIENT INFORMATION AND CLINICAL FINDINGS

2.1. Demographic and Presenting Details

Age/Sex: 42-year-old male

Occupation: School teacher (noted for potential stress correlation and high facial expression usage)

Chief Complaints: Sudden onset, 4 days prior, of

1. Deviation of the mouth to the left side.
2. Inability to close the right eye completely.
3. Slurring of speech.
4. Difficulty in chewing and retaining food on the right side.

History of Present Illness: Symptoms appeared abruptly upon waking, with no preceding trauma. No history of ear pain, rash, or recent vaccination.

2.2. Medical and Personal History

✚ **Medical History:** No known comorbidities like Diabetes Mellitus or Hypertension. No recent history of viral infection.

✚ **Personal History:** Vegetarian diet. Occasional sleep deprivation due to work. Moderate stress levels reported.

✚ Ayurvedic Assessment (Dashavidha Pariksha)

1. Prakriti: Vata-Pitta
2. Vikriti: Predominantly Vata
3. Samhanana: Madhyama (Medium)
4. Satva: Madhyama (Medium)
5. Ahara Shakti: Madhyama
6. Vyayama Shakti: Madhyama
7. Nadi: Vata-predominant (fast, thin, irregular pulse)
8. Mala/Mutra: Normal
9. Jihva: Slightly dry, coated
10. Sabda/Sparsha: Speech slurred; skin dry to touch.

2.3. Clinical Examination (Ashtasthana Pariksha)

Local Examination (Face)

Inspection: Marked asymmetry at rest. Right nasolabial fold flattened. Mouth deviated to the left on attempted smile or showing teeth. Inability to wrinkle the forehead on the right side (loss of frontalis function). Right palpebral fissure wider; incomplete eye closure (Lagophthalmos ~4mm). Bell's phenomenon present.

Dynamic Tests: Inability to puff the right cheek, whistle, or fully close the right eye against resistance.

House-Brackmann Facial Nerve Grading System (Modern Correlation): Grade IV/V – Moderately severe dysfunction.^[9]

3. DIAGNOSIS

3.1. Ayurvedic Diagnosis: Ardita (Vataja)

The diagnosis was established based on the classical features described in texts:

✚ Mukhavakrata (deviation of mouth)

- ✚ Akshivinimilia/Akshighuna (improper eye movement/closure)
- ✚ Vakrastuta (altered speech)
- ✚ Sudden onset (Vata Lakshana)
- ✚ Nadi showing Vata predominance.

Etiology was attributed to factors potentially aggravating Vata, such as stress, irregular sleep, and seasonal influences (likely Grishma/Sharad Ritu transition).^[10]

3.2. Modern Correlation: Idiopathic Facial Palsy (Bell's Palsy)

The acute, unilateral, lower motor neuron type facial paralysis with no identifiable cause (like stroke, trauma, or ear infection) was consistent with a diagnosis of Bell's Palsy.^[11]

4. TREATMENT PLAN AND MATERIALS

4.1. Objectives of Treatment

1. Shamana: Pacify the aggravated Vata Dosha.
2. Srotoshodhana: Clear the vitiated channels (Siras & Snayu) of the face.
3. Brimhana: Nourish and strengthen the affected nerves and muscles (Dhatu).
4. Vata-Anulomana: Normalize the direction and function of Vata.

4.2. Treatment Protocol

The treatment was divided into three phases over 7 consecutive days.

A. Internal Medications (Anushna Sevana)

1. Dashamoola Kwatha: 40 ml, twice daily on empty stomach. Rationale: Dashamoola is a potent Vatashamaka formulation. Its deep-acting properties help pacify Vata systemically and clear obstructed channels.^[12]

2. Ashwagandha Churna (Withania somnifera): 3 grams, twice daily with warm milk. Rationale: A renowned Balya and Rasayana drug, it supports nerve tissue (Majja Dhatu) and muscle (Mamsa Dhatu) strength, combating the Bala Kshaya (loss of strength) caused by Vata.^[13]

3. Rasnadi Churna: Used for external application (Lepa) on the scalp and forehead after Nasya. Rationale: Provides local Vata-pacifying and soothing effects.

B. Main Procedure: Bala Dhatryadi Taila Matra Nasya

Drug: Bala Dhatryadi Taila (prepared as per Sahasrayogam text).^[8]

Pharmacological Rationale of Key Ingredients:

- ✚ **Bala (*Sida cordifolia*):** Balya (strengthening), Vatahara, Shothahara (anti-inflammatory). Rich in alkaloids with potential neuroprotective effects.^[14]
- ✚ **Dhatri/Amalaki (*Emblica officinalis*):** Tridoshahara, especially Vatapitta, Rasayana. Its high Vitamin C and antioxidant properties may support neural repair.^[15]
- ✚ **Tila Taila (Sesame Oil):** The base, inherently Vatashamaka, acts as an effective Anupana (vehicle) for drug delivery.^[16]

Procedure (Adopted from Classical References)^[17,18]

I. Purva Karma (Preparatory Procedures)

1. **Abhyanga:** Gentle whole-body and focused facial massage with Murchhita Tila Taila (processed sesame oil) for 15 minutes. This prepares the Srotas (microchannels) and softens the tissues.
2. **Mridu Swedana:** Mild fomentation over the face and neck using a warm cloth. This further liquefies and mobilizes Doshas.

II. Pradhana Karma (Main Procedure):

1. The patient was made to lie in a supine position with the head slightly extended (Shayana).
2. After checking for proper nostril patency, lukewarm Bala Dhatriyadi Taila was instilled as Matra Nasya (sub-therapeutic dose), 8 drops in each nostril successively using a dropper, with inhalation.
3. The patient was instructed to take a slight sniff to draw the oil upward and then remain in the same position for 2 minutes.

III. Paschat Karma (Post-Procedural Care)

1. Dhoomapana: Inhalation of medicated smoke from Vacha (*Acorus calamus*) and Haridra (*Curcuma longa*) for 3-4 puffs. This clears the nasal passages and prevents sinus complications.
2. Gandusha/Kavala: Gargling with lukewarm Dashamoola Kwatha. This strengthens the vocal cords and throat muscles.
3. Advice to avoid cold exposure, direct wind, excessive speech, and daytime sleep.

Duration: The entire protocol, including Nasya, was administered for 7 consecutive days.

5. Assessment Criteria and Methodology

Assessment was performed daily before treatment. Parameters were adapted from classical Ardita symptoms and modern facial nerve grading scales.^[9,19]

Assessment Parameter	0-Point (Severe)	1-Point (Moderate)	2-Point (Mild)	3-Point (Normal)
1. Eye Closure (Lagophthalmos)	>5mm gap, no effort	3-5mm gap, weak effort	1-2mm gap, moderate effort	Complete closure, strong
2. Deviation of Mouth	Severe deviation at rest	Obvious deviation on movement	Slight deviation only on smile	Symmetrical at rest & movement
3. Forehead Wrinkling	No movement	Barely perceptible movement	Partial wrinkling, asymmetry	Full symmetrical wrinkling
4. Cheek Puffing	Air escapes immediately	Weak puff, cannot hold	Moderate puff, holds briefly	Full puff, holds firmly
5. Speech & Mastication	Severe slurring, constant dribbling	Noticeable slurring, frequent dribbling	Mild slurring, occasional dribbling	Clear speech, no dribbling

Total Score: 15 (Normal).

6. RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

The patient's progress was meticulously recorded. The total assessment score improved from a baseline of 4/15 to 13/15 by Day 7.

Baseline (Day 1): Score 4. Severe lagophthalmos (5mm), mouth deviated at rest, no forehead movement, inability to puff cheek, marked slurring.

Day 3: Score 7. Slight improvement noted. Eye closure gap reduced to 4mm. Minimal movement observed at the right mouth angle on smiling. Patient reported a tingling sensation on the right face, interpreted as a positive sign of nerve responsiveness (Vata Anulomana).

Day 5: Score 10. Significant improvement. Eye closure gap reduced to 2mm (could close eye with mild effort). Facial asymmetry at rest was greatly reduced. Partial forehead wrinkling returned. Cheek puffing was weak but present. Speech was clearer.

Day 7: Score 13. Marked improvement. Near-complete eye closure (1mm gap). Symmetrical smile with minimal deviation. Good forehead movement. Could puff cheek and hold air with moderate strength. Speech was clear, and mastication was normal. The patient expressed high satisfaction. No adverse effects from the Nasya or other treatments were reported.

7. DISCUSSION

The rapid and significant recovery observed in this case of Ardita can be attributed to the multifaceted, targeted approach of the Ayurvedic protocol, with Bala Dhatriyadi Taila Nasya at its core.

7.1. Pathophysiological Rationale and Mode of Action

Ardita is a classic Vata Vriddhi and Margavarodha Janya Vikara (disease caused by obstruction in channels).^[4] Aggravated Vata, possessing Ruksha (dry) and Khara (rough) properties, depletes the local Kapha and Pitta, leading to loss of muscle tone and nerve conduction. Nasya, specifically Shamana-type Matra Nasya with a Brimhana (nourishing) oil, directly counters this.

Direct Drug Delivery: The nasal mucosa offers a direct pathway to the brain (Shiras) via olfactory and trigeminal neural pathways, bypassing the blood-brain barrier to some extent.^[7,20] Bala Dhatriyadi Taila, with its lipophilic nature, is absorbed effectively.

Vata Shamana at the Site: The Snigdha (unctuous) and Ushna (warm) properties of the Taila counteract the Ruksha and Sheeta Guna of aggravated Vata in the facial nerves and muscles.^[21]

Srotoshodhana: The combined effect of Abhyanga, Swedana, and Nasya helps clear the Avarana (obstruction) in the Siras of the face, facilitating the restoration of normal Vata flow (Vata Anulomana).^[22]

Neuro-muscular Nourishment (Brimhana & Balya): Ingredients like Bala and Ashwagandha are documented for their nerve-tonic and muscle-strengthening properties. Modern studies suggest they may support neurite outgrowth and reduce neuronal inflammation^[13,14]

7.2. Synergistic Role of Adjunct Therapies

- ✚ **Dashamoola Kwatha** provided systemic Vata pacification.
- ✚ **Ashwagandha Churna** acted as a systemic Rasayana and Majjavaha Srotas rejuvenator, aiding in long-term recovery and preventing recurrence.^[23]
- ✚ **Purva Karma (Abhyanga & Swedana)** was crucial in preparing the tissue bed for optimal drug absorption and Dosha mobilization.

7.3. Correlation with Modern Concepts

The intranasal route's efficacy in Bell's Palsy can be correlated with the potential delivery of anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective agents to the inflamed facial nerve near the stylomastoid foramen via neuronal and vascular connections.^[24] The reduction in inflammation and edema may decompress the nerve, facilitating recovery—a principle analogous to the action of steroids but achieved through herbal pharmacodynamics.

7.4. Limitations of this Study

As a single-case study, the findings, though compelling, cannot be generalized. The natural history of Bell's Palsy includes spontaneous recovery in a significant percentage of cases. However, the rapid trajectory of recovery (within 7 days) observed here is notable, as spontaneous recovery often takes weeks. The absence of a control group is a limitation. Future double-blind, randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes and objective electrophysiological measurements (like EMG) are warranted to validate these findings.^[25]

8. CONCLUSION

This case study demonstrates that a structured Ayurvedic treatment protocol, with a primary focus on Bala Dhatryadi Taila Matra Nasya, can lead to rapid and significant clinical improvement in patients with Ardita (Bell's Palsy). The intervention worked on the core Ayurvedic pathophysiology by pacifying Vata, clearing obstructed channels, and nourishing nerve tissue. The results highlight the scientific validity and clinical relevance of Nasya Karma as a targeted drug delivery system for neurological disorders of the head and neck. This approach offers a safe, effective, and holistic alternative or adjunct to conventional management, meriting further rigorous scientific exploration.

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